

High Performance Poisson Equation Solver for Hybrid CPU/GPU Systems

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Abstract

We investigated the possible way for treatment of electrostatic interactions by solving numerically Poisson's equation using Conjugate Gradient method and Stabilized BiConjugate Gradient method. The aim of the research was to test the execution time of prototype programs running on BLueGene/P and CPU/GPU system. The results show that the tested methods are applicable for electrostatics treatment in molecular-dynamics simulations.

1. Introduction

Electrostatic interactions treatment is very important when one models biologically important interactions at atomistic and molecular level by means of molecular –dynamics simulations. We investigated the possible way to do this by directly solving the Poisson's equation.

The divergence of the electrostatic field in vacuum is specified by the differential form of Gauss' law

$$\nabla \cdot \vec{E}(\vec{r}) = \frac{\rho(\vec{r})}{\epsilon} .$$

(1)

The curl of the electrostatic field is specified by the static form of Faraday's law

$$\nabla \times \vec{E}(\vec{r}) = 0 .$$

(2)

By Helmholtz' theorem, these two first-order vector differential relations completely determine the electrostatic field vector $\vec{E}(\vec{r})$ in any specified region of space given as a consequence of (2), the electrostatic field may be expressed as

$$\vec{E} = -\nabla\phi(\vec{r}), \quad (3)$$

where $\phi(\vec{r})$ is the scalar potential.

Substitution of (3) into Gauss' Law (1) then yields Poisson's equation

$$\nabla^2\phi = -\frac{\rho}{\epsilon} \text{ or } (\phi_{xx} + \phi_{yy} + \phi_{zz}) = -\rho/\epsilon. \quad (4)$$

In a discretized form this can be written as

$$(\phi_{xx})_{ijk} + (\phi_{yy})_{ijk} + (\phi_{zz})_{ijk} = -f_{ijk}. \quad (5)$$

Let us denote (i, j, k) three-dimensional lattice indices and $(\phi_{\alpha\alpha})_{ijk}$ is an approximation to the second partial derivative with respect to the coordinate direction $\alpha\alpha$.

Denote second-order difference operator as

$$(\phi_{\alpha\alpha})_{ijk} = \frac{1}{h_\alpha^2} \delta_\alpha^2 \phi_{ijk}, \quad (6)$$

where h_α is the grid spacing in direction α and δ_α^2 is the second-order difference operator

$$\begin{aligned} \delta_x^2 &= \phi_{i-1,y,k} - 2\phi_{i,j,k} + \phi_{i+1,j,k}, \\ \delta_y^2 &= \phi_{i,y-1,k} - 2\phi_{i,j,k} + \phi_{i,j+1,k}, \\ \delta_z^2 &= \phi_{i,y,k-1} - 2\phi_{i,j,k} + \phi_{i,j,k+1}. \end{aligned}$$

Standard and high-order finite difference operators of the Poisson's equation are derived from the approximation

$$\frac{\partial^2\phi}{\partial\alpha^2} \Big|_{\alpha=ih_\alpha} = \frac{4}{h_\alpha^2} \left(\sinh^{-1} \frac{\delta_\alpha}{2} \right)^2 = \frac{1}{h_\alpha^2} \delta_\alpha^2 \left\{ 1 - \frac{1}{12} \delta_\alpha^2 + \frac{1}{90} \delta_\alpha^4 - \frac{1}{560} \delta_\alpha^6 \pm \dots \right\} \phi_{ijk},$$

where α is x, y or z .

To solve the three dimensional Poisson's equations in Cartesian coordinate systems using finite difference approximations; see e.g. [1]

We have developed an approximation using central difference scheme to obtain a 19-point stencil and a 27-point stencil with some modification in the right hand side terms

The grid size along the x, y and z directions is $h=0.5\text{\AA}(\text{Angstrom})$; $i=1,2,3,\dots,m$; $j=1,2,3,\dots,n$; $k=1,2,3,\dots,p$; $m = x/h$; $n = y/h$; $p = z/h$; $\rho = \frac{q}{h^3}$, where q is point electric charge.

For 27-point stencil finite difference approximations if finite difference operator (6) for the unknowns $\varphi(i,j,k)$ are obtained the following equation :

Figure 1: 27-points Laplacian

$$144h^2\rho = -600\varphi_{i,j,k} + 60[\varphi_{i,j,k-1} + \varphi_{i,j,k+1}] + 60[\varphi_{i-1,j,k} + \varphi_{i+1,j,k} + \varphi_{i,j-1,k} + \varphi_{i,j+1,k} + 18\varphi_{i-1,j-1,k} + \varphi_{i-1,j+1,k} + \varphi_{i+1,j-1,k} + \varphi_{i+1,j+1,k} + 18[\varphi_{i-1,j,k-1} + \varphi_{i+1,j,k-1} + \varphi_{i-1,j,k+1} + \varphi_{i+1,j,k+1} + \varphi_{i,j-1,k-1} + \varphi_{i,j+1,k-1} + \varphi_{i,j-1,k+1} + \varphi_{i,j+1,k+1} + 3\varphi_{i+1,j-1,k-1} + \varphi_{i-1,j-1,k-1} + \varphi_{i+1,j+1,k-1} + \varphi_{i+1,j+1,k+1} + \varphi_{i-1,j-1,k+1} + \varphi_{i+1,j-1,k+1} + \varphi_{i-1,j+1,k-1} + \varphi_{i-1,j+1,k+1}] \quad (7)$$

The maximum absolute error of approximation of the $\varphi(\vec{r})$ is $O(h^{-6})$.

Taking first the X-direction, next Y-direction and lastly Z-direction in (7) we get a large system of linear equations (the number of equations actually depends on the values of m , n and p); and this system of equations can be written in matrix form as

$$Au(s) = b(s), \quad (8)$$

where

of the grid (64, 64,512) and calculation time and speedup are presented in **Figure 3**. One can find the corresponding number in **Table 1** and **Table 2** respectively.

Table 1 The matrix-vector and scalar products per iteration and total execution time

grid dimensions 128x128x1024 = 16777216 cells				accuracy 1e-6
per interaction				201 iterations
bgp cores	matrix-vector [ms]	scalar product [ms]	halo exchange [ms]	calc time [s]
16	91.72	13.17	0.79	64.02
32	45.84	6.98	0.97	32.33
64	22.80	3.40	0.97	15.33
128	11.34	1.93	1.13	7.89
256	5.55	1.11	1.13	4.11
512	2.72	0.38	1.13	2.24
1024	1.31	0.27	1.13	1.37

Figure 2 Vector-Matrix multiplication – calculation time (blue line) and speed up (pink line)

Figure 3 Conjugate Gradient method calculation time (blue line) and speed up (pink line)

Table 2 The matrix-vector and scalar products per iteration speedup and total execution speedup

bgp cores	per iteration			201 iterations
	Matrix-Vector multiplication speedup	scalar product speedup	halo exchange speedup	calc time speedup
16	1.00	1.00	1.00	1.00
32	2.00	1.89	0.82	1.98
64	4.02	3.88	0.82	4.18
128	8.09	6.82	0.71	8.11
256	16.51	11.88	0.70	15.59
512	33.77	34.23	0.70	28.61
1024	70.27	49.11	0.70	46.87

The parallel CPU-GPU algorithm

For the solution of the systems of linear algebraic equations we created new parallel Biconjugate Gradients Stabilized algorithm (BiCGSTAB).
Classical BiCGSTAB algorithm

The initial guess:

$$\begin{aligned}\phi^0 &= 0 \\ s^0 &= B \\ z^0 &= B \\ k &= 0\end{aligned}$$

L1:

$$\begin{aligned}k &= k + 1 \\ x^{k-1} &= \phi^k \\ F^k &= A x^{k-1} = A \phi^k \\ r^{k-1} &= F^k - B \\ z^k &= A s^{k-1} \\ \alpha &= (r^{k-1}, r^{k-1}) / (s^{k-1}, z^k) \\ x^k &= x^{k-1} + \alpha s^{k-1} \\ r^k &= r^{k-1} - \alpha z^k \\ s^k &= r^k + [(r^k, r^k) / (r^{k-1}, r^{k-1})] s^{k-1} \\ \phi &= x^k\end{aligned}$$

if $(r^k, r^k) > \varepsilon(B, B)$ *go to* L1
else STOP;
end if;

$k=0$

$$\begin{aligned}
F^k &= A\phi^k \\
r^k &= F^k - B \\
z^{k+1} &= As^k \\
\alpha &= (r^k, r^k) / (s^k, z^{k+1}) \\
\phi^{k+1} &= \phi^k + \alpha s^k \\
r^{k+1} &= r^k - \alpha z^{k+1} \\
s^{k+1} &= r^{k+1} + [(r^{k+1}, r^{k+1}) / (r^k, r^k)] s^k
\end{aligned}$$

if $(r^k, r^k) > \varepsilon(B, B)$ go to L1

$k=k+1$

else STOP;

end if;

The multiplications Ap and As take the longest time to calculate. The number of arithmetic operations “multiplication and addition” is $27MNP$ for each of the two multiplications.

Parallel BiCGSTAB solver [2]

We assume that the number of modules Intel-Xeon Phi is equal to at least the number of rows p of matrix A .

1. The row A_k of matrix A and block b_k of vector b as well as the initial value of blocks x_{k-1} , x_k , x_{k+1} of vector x are sent to the k^{th} CPU/GPU node.
2. All GPUs simultaneously calculate $\delta_k^0 = S^*x_{k-1} + R^*x_k + S^*x_{k+1}$, by parallel treatment of N threads, each with length M . The maximum number of threads depends on the GPU type.
We obtain $r_k^0 = b_k - \delta_k^0$, $r_k = r_k^0$, $p_k = r_k$ and the constant $\rho_k = (r_k, r_k^0)$.
3. Each GPU sends the vectors r_k^0 , r_k and the constant ρ_k to the corresponding CPUs. Afterwards CPUs communicate and the vectors $r = r_0$, $p = p_0$ and the constant $\rho = \sum \rho_k$ are obtained by collective communication.
4. CPU sends the blocks p_{k-1} , p_k , p_{k+1} of vector p and r_{k-1} , r_k , r_{k+1} of vector r to GPU. $k=1, 2, \dots, P$
5. All GPUs simultaneously calculate the blocks $u_k = S^*p_{k-1} + R^*p_k + S^*p_{k+1}$ by parallel treatment of N threads, each with length M . The constant $\gamma_k = (r_k^0, u_k)$ is calculated.
6. CPU (master) calculates the constant $\alpha = \rho / \sum \gamma_k$ and sends it to other CPUs and then they send it to GPUs. The latter calculate $s_k = r_k - \alpha u_k$.
7. s_k are sent to CPU (master), which constructs the vector s and sends the triplet s_{k-1} , s_k , s_{k+1} to the k^{th} CPU and then they send it to GPUs. $k=1, 2, \dots, P$

8. The same way as in point 5, - $t_k = S^*s_{k-1} + R^*s_k + S^*s_{k+1}$. The constants $\tau_k = (t_k, t_k)$ and $\sigma_k = (t_k, s_k)$ are sent to CPU (master), which calculates $\tau = \sum \tau_k$, $\sigma = \sum \sigma_k$ and $\omega = \sigma/\tau$.
9. The k^{th} GPU calculates the new x_k u r_k . x_k , r_k and u_k are sent to CPU and then to CPU (master)
10. The constants β and ρ and the new vector p are calculated.
11. If the error $\text{abs}(r)$ is greater than ε , then the cycle repeats from point 3. Else STOP

If the number of GPUs is at least equal to P, and the number of the threads is less or equal than N, then the number of arithmetic operations is proportional to 54M. Hence, **the speedup** of Parallel BiCGSTAB solver in comparison to the classical BiCGSTAB method **is proportional to PN**.

If the number of Xeon Phi modules is K, and the number of the threads $N > 240$, then the **speedup** is proportional to **PN/(Res+1)(L+1)**), where

$$Res = \text{int}\left(\frac{P}{K}\right)$$

$$L = \text{int}\left(\frac{N}{240}\right)$$

A Poisson solver using 27-point stencil has been developed using CUDA. It is based on the classical Biconjugate gradient stabilized method. The current version is made in such a way that everything is stored in the host memory and the GPU is used only for parallel calculations. In order to obtain this goal two way communications was needed. The block diagram of the implemented algorithm is shown in Figure 4. The vector-scalar and vector-vector operations are computed by the CPU. In the case of vector matrix multiplication the vector data are transferred to the GPU memory and the multiplication is done by the device in shared memory programming model manner. The result is returned back to the host memory. The time required for all these processes has been measured. At the current stage of development, it is assumed that it will be a faster method to calculate indexes of nonzero elements and their values based on their row number. This is easily achieved using three nested "for" loops.

Figure 4 Block diagram of CPU/GPU implementation of BiCGSTAB method.

Figure 5 Timing of data transfer from CPU to GPU (red line), from GPU to CPU (blue line), and execution time of matrix-vector multiplication (green line)

Two versions of the test program were used in order to estimate the speedup of the hybrid CPU/GPU code. The first one solves the problem using only the CPU while the hybrid one runs according to the algorithm presented in Figure 4. The benchmark tests were run on a computer system with 1 CPU (Intel(R) Core(TM) i7-2600 CPU @ 3.40GHz) and 1 NVIDIA GPU card (Geforce GTX 580). The time need for data transfer, to and from the GPU device and matrix-vector upon the vector size is depicted in Figure 5. The last ones scale linearly with the problem size.

Figure 6: The execution time of CPU only (green line) and hybrid CPU/GPU (red line) as a function of the problem size (the size of the edge of the cubic grid in number of cells)

The total execution time of both test programs as a function of problem size (the edge length of the cubic grid in number of cells) is shown in Figure 6. One can easily see that there is a certain size of the problem at which the CPU version execution time is equal to the execution time of the hybrid version. Below this problem size the time for data transfer to and from the GPU device is significantly longer than the time need for matrix-vector multiplication on the CPU and it does not worth using the accelerator. The speedup if the hybrid version saturates for the grid size bigger than about $70 \times 70 \times 70$ cells and has the value of 10 (see Figure 7). Our current work is focused on changing the concept of data storage and making the program to use multiple GPU-s using MPI parallelism.

3. Conclusion

We have developed routines to calculate Poisson's equation and tested them on BlueGene/P architecture and on a CPU/GPU node. The obtained results show linear scalability of matrix-vector multiplication with the size of the problem. The finite time needed for the data transfer from the CPU to the GPU and back implies a limit below which communication time is comparable and longer then calculation time. The limit depends on the computer system where the calculations take place but it is well below the modern science problems size. The timing tests done in the present work underline the advantage of using GPU acceleration unit for solving the Poisson's equation for problems one can meet in the practice. However, there

are possible ways for optimizing the code and our implementation should be considered as an upper limit of the performance of the BiCGSTAB algorithm.

Figure 7: Speedup of hybrid CPU/GPU code with respect to the CPU only version.

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References

1. W. F. Spitz and G. F. Carey, Formulation for the 3D Poisson Equation,” Numerical Methods for Partial Differential Equations, Vol. 12, No. 2, 1996, pp. 235-243.
2. Sleijpen, G. L. G.; Fokkema, D. R. (November 1993). "BiCGstab(l) for linear equations involving unsymmetric matrices with complex spectrum" (PDF). Electronic Transactions on Numerical Analysis (Kent, OH: Kent State University) 1: 11–32. ISSN 1068-9613